

All Patient Cases (images and clinical data) collected until 23/04/2024 in the CHAIMELEON Repository related to Prostate cancer.

ID: 05674e3a-596e-40e8-97a5-21846fef19a3

URL: <https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/05674e3a-596e-40e8-97a5-21846fef19a3/details>

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 991

Subjects count: 909

Age range: Between 46 years and 965 years

Sex: Male, Unkown

Body part(s): PROSTATE, PELVIS, ARM, ABDOMEN, Pelvis^Masculin, HEAD, PANCREAS, CHESTABDPELVIS, ABDOMENPELVIS, LUMBAR SPINE, Unknown

Modality: MR, CT, PT, Unknown